

Spectral and Magnetic Studies of Manganese(II) Complexes

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Synthetic and characterization studies of diaqua manganese(II)-tetra thiourea dichloride complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, and its mixed ligand complexes with various nitrogen donor ligands are reported. These complexes have been characterized by magnetic, diffuse reflectance and infrared spectral studies apart from the elemental analyses. The diffuse reflectance spectra were performed and values of Racah inter-electronic repulsion parameter B and C, Slater-Condon-Shortly parameter F_2 and F_4 , crystal field splitting energy (Dq), nephelauxetic ratio (β) and nephelauxetic parameter for coordinated ligand (h_x) have been calculated. From infrared studies it has been possible to assign whether the thiourea molecules present in complexes are coordinated to the metal ion through sulfur or nitrogen atom.

MANGANESE(II) ion has d^5 configuration and is capable of forming spin-free as well as spin-paired complexes. Due to the additional stability of the half filled d-shell, the spin-free complexes are most predominant. The equilibrium constant for their formation in aqueous solution are not high as compared to those for bivalent cations of succeeding element (Fe^{2+} - Cu^{2+}), because of manganese(II) is the largest of these and it has no ligand field stabilization energy in its complexes¹. Manganese(II) complexes are susceptible to oxidation^{2,3}, but the complexes synthesized in the present study have been found to be sufficiently stable and resist oxidation. In these ligand exchange reactions, the comparatively weak bonded water molecules of parent diaqua-tetrathiourea manganese(II) dichloride complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, are quantitatively replaced by nitrogen donor ligand or ligands. The spectra in the solution however, could not be obtained because of the weak intensity of the bands and lack of the high solubility of these complexes in organic solvents and hence diffuse reflectance spectra have been carried out.

Experimental

Preparation of diaqua tetrathiourea manganese(II) dichloride complex, $(\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2)\text{Cl}_2$:

Manganese(II) chloride tetrahydrate (19.78 gm ; 0.1 mol) and thiourea (30.44 gm : 0.4 mol) were added to ethanol (300 ml). About 10 ml of water was then added to increase the solubility of the reactants. The reaction mixture was refluxed for three hours, on cooling the crystals of complex were separated. The crystals were filtered, washed with small portions of ethanol and dried under vacuum. Yield = 41 gm ; 80%. Melting point 131°. Elemental analyses data are given in the Table 1.

Preparation of mixed ligand complexes :

To a hot solution of diaqua tetrathiourea manganese(II) dichloride complex (0.01 mol) in dry ethanol (60 ml) was added an ethanolic solution of the ligand viz. pyridine or aniline or quinoline (0.02 mol), or 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridine or

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, MELTING POINT AND MAGNETIC MOMENT

Complex	% Metal		% Nitrogen		% Sulfur		M.P. in °C	μ_{eff} (in B.M.)
	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found		
$[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	11.78	11.8	24.03	24.1	27.50	27.4	131	5.98
$[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{py})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	9.33	9.2	23.80	23.7	21.79	21.8	144	5.95
$[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{phen})]\text{Cl}_2$	8.99	9.0	22.94	22.9	21.00	20.9	350*	6.12
$[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{bipy})]\text{Cl}_2$	9.36	9.3	23.88	23.9	21.86	21.9	350*	6.14
$[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{qu})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	7.95	7.9	20.29	20.2	18.58	18.5	83	6.21
$[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{ani})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	8.91	8.8	22.72	22.7	20.81	20.7	110	6.00
$[\text{Mn}(\text{tu})_4(\text{en})]\text{Cl}_2$	11.20	11.2	28.56	28.5	26.15	26.1	102	6.16

tu=Thiourea ; py=Pyridine ; phen=1,10-Phenanthroline ; bipy=2,2'-Bipyridine ; qu=quinoline ; ani=Aniline ; en=Ethylenediamine ; μ_{eff} =Magnetic moment ; * =Do not melt.

ethylenediamine (0.01 mol). On cooling, the complex separated out from the solution. It was filtered washed with ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. Purity of these complexes was checked by elemental analyses (Table 1) manganese(II) was estimated⁴ as $\text{MnNH}_4\text{PO}_4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Physical Measurements :

Magnetic measurements were carried out on Gouy magnetic balance at $300 \pm 1^\circ\text{K}$. Diffuse reflectance spectra in the UV and visible region were recorded on a VEB Carl Zeiss Jena VSU-2 Spectrophotometer using an annular ring type attachment o/r. The infrared spectra of these complexes have been recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 Spectrophotometer in KBr pallet in the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

Manganese(II) complexes are generally spin-free complexes. Since spin-free manganese(II) complexes have an orbitally non-degenerate 6s ground term, spin-only magnetic moment of 5.92 B.M. is expected which will be independent of the temperature and the stereochemistry^{5,6}. In present course of study the complexes show magnetic moment value in the range 5.95-6.21 B. M. (Table 1) suggesting thereby that these are spin-free complexes having five unpaired electrons.

The electronic spectra of manganese(II) complexes show that bands are weak in intensity and number of bands is quite large. In Mn(II) complexes the intensity of the electronic transitions from the ground state 6s to the states of four fold multiplicity are very weak and since Mn(II) has a d five electronic configuration the same type of energy-level diagram applies whether the metal ion is surrounded by tetrahedral or octahedral environment. In hexaaqua manganese(II), six electronic bands in two groups of three have been observed¹. Only four bands could be observed in the diffuse reflectance spectra of manganese(II) complexes studied in the present work. These four observed bands representing corresponding transitions and energy in terms of Racah parameter⁷ are viz. $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g} (^4G)$, $(10B+5C)$, $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g (^4G)$, $^4A_{1g} (^4G)$, $(10B+5C)$, $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g (^4D)$, $(17B+5C)$ and $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g} (^4P)$, $(7B+7C)$. Diffuse reflectance spectra for some complexes have been plotted in remission function vs wave length (Fig. 1). Kubelka-Munk remission function $F=(1-R)^2/2R$, was used as a measure of absorption by powdered sample, where R is the diffuse reflectance. The electronic spectral pattern of all the complexes has been found to be similar.

The experimentally observed transition energies and calculated values for parameters B, C, Dq and β are summarized in the Table 2. The values obtained for the parameters B and C by using the transitions $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g} (^4G)$ and $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g} (^4P)$ are negative which have no physical significance, while

Fig. 1.

the transitions $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g$, $^4A_{1g} (^4G)$ and $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g} (^4P)$ yield the absurd values for parameter B and hence values are not included in the table. The best set of values for parameter B and C could be obtained using transitions $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g$, $^4A_{1g} (^4G)$ and $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g (^4D)$, this is due to the fact that the energies of these two transitions are independent on crystal field splitting energy and depends⁸ only on the parameters B and C. The value for the parameter Dq could be evaluated with the help of curve transition energies vs Dq, given by Orgel⁹ using the energy level due to transition $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g} (^4G)$. The value for parameter Dq could not be obtained using the transitions $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g$, $^4A_{1g} (^4G)$ and $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_g (^4D)$, because these transitions are independent of Dq, with almost zero slope. Parameter B and C are linear combination of certain coulomb and exchange integral and are generally treated as empirical parameters obtained from the spectra of the free ions. Slater-Condon-Shortly parameter F_2 and F_4 are related to Racah interelectronic repulsion parameter B and C as follow¹⁰: $B=F_2-5F_4$ and $C=35F_4$. By using values of Racah parameter B and C, values for parameter F_2 and F_4 have been calculated (Table 2).

The electron-electron repulsion in complex is less than in the free ion, resulting in an increase distance between electrons and thus an effective increase in the size of the orbitals. On increasing delocalization the β decreases and is less than one in complex. Estimate of β has been obtained from the nephelauxetic parameter for ligand (h_x) and nephelauxetic parameter of the metal ion (K_M) as¹¹: $(1-\beta)=h_x \cdot K_M$. The values for parameter h_x for the complex have been calculated using covalency-contribution of manganese(II) ion (0.07), while the numerical value 786 cm^{-1} for parameter B of free Mn^{2+} ion⁷ is used to calculate value for the β . It has been observed that the lower value of β and higher value of h_x for mixed ligand complexes as

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL TRANSITION ENERGIES, CALCULATED VALUES FOR PARAMETERS B, C, F₂, F₄, Dq (IN CM⁻¹) β AND h_x

Complex	⁶ A _{1g} ↓ ⁴ T _{1g} (⁴ P)	⁶ A _{1g} ↓ ⁴ E _g (⁴ D)	⁶ A _{1g} ↓ ⁴ E _g , ⁴ A _{1g} (⁴ G)	⁶ A _{1g} ↓ ⁴ T _{1g} (⁴ G)	B	C	F ₂	F ₄	Dq	β	h _x
[Mn(tu) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	32258	29411	24390	20618	717.0	3444	1194	95	763	0.91	1.25
[Mn(tu) ₄ (py) ₂]Cl ₂	27855	24875	24875	20000	425.7	4123	1034	117	850	0.54	6.54
[Mn(tu) ₄ (phen)]Cl ₂	33557	27777	24271	19801	500.8	3852	1050	110	873	0.63	5.18
[Mn(tu) ₄ (bipy)]Cl ₂	32786	28169	23809	19607	622.8	3516	1124	100	895	0.79	2.96
[Mn(tu) ₄ (qu) ₂]Cl ₂	32786	28818	24096	19801	674.5	3470	1170	99	873	0.85	2.02
[Mn(tu) ₄ (ani) ₂]Cl ₂	33333	28328	24096	20000	604.5	3610	1120	103	850	0.76	3.92
[Mn(tu) ₄ (en)]Cl ₂	33003	27932	24154	19531	539.7	3751	1075	107	901	0.68	4.47

compared to the parent complex indicate the increase in covalent character on further complexation. Like other octahedral manganese(II) complexes the complexes studied in the present work yield light coloured solution with weak intensity in solution indicating most probably the octahedral environment around metal ion.

The infrared spectrum of the parent complex has confirmed the presence of coordinated water molecules by a band at 3460 cm⁻¹, whereas, the mixed ligand complexes derived from it do not show absorption in this region, indicating the replacement of coordinated water molecules by second ligand or ligands.

The S→M bond formation is expected to increase the contribution of the highly polar structure H₂N=C-S⁻ to the thiourea molecule. This naturally will result in the greater double bond character for the N-C bond, while at the same time C-S bond will attain greater single bond character^{1,2}. The high frequency medium-strong-NH absorption bands in the spectrum of thiourea shift to higher frequency region and the strong band observed at 730 cm⁻¹ in

thiourea shifts to lower frequency region on complexation support the sulfur coordination of thiourea ligand³. The strong band occurring at 1617 cm⁻¹ in thiourea assigned to-NH₂ deformation; shifts to 1600 cm⁻¹ in the complex. The intense band occurring at 1413 cm⁻¹ in thiourea is assigned to-NH₂ rocking. The N-C-N stretching vibration of thiourea molecule which is shown in the form of absorption around 1473 cm⁻¹ moves to higher frequency region (1480 cm⁻¹) indicating most probably the greater double bond character of C-N bond on complex formation. The intensity of the strong absorption band at 1083 cm⁻¹ in thiourea diminishes on the complex formation. This is most probably due to the considerable change in the nature of the N-C bond and C=S bond on coordination of thiourea through sulfur atom^{14,15}. A band ~410 cm⁻¹ in complexes correspond to a band at 411 cm⁻¹ in thiourea may be assigned to-NH₂ torsional. The significant IR bands due to coordinated thiourea in different complexes are summarized in Table 3. In addition to the bands due to coordinated thiourea ligand the position of bands of the second ligand present in mixed ligand complexes are also modified on complexation showing their coordination to the metal atom.

TABLE 3—SIGNIFICANT IR BANDS (IN CM⁻¹) DUE TO COORDINATED THIOUREA AND THEIR ASSIGNMENT

Thio urea	[Mn(tu) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	[Mn(tu) ₄ (py) ₂]Cl ₂	[Mn(tu) ₄ (phen)]Cl ₂	[Mn(tu) ₄ (bipy)]Cl ₂	[Mn(tu) ₄ (qu) ₂]Cl ₂	[Mn(tu) ₄ (ani) ₂]Cl ₂	[Mn(tu) ₄ (en)]Cl ₂	Assignment
3365s	3375s	3380s	3380m	3382m	3360s	3385s	3380s	
3260s	3285s	3275m	3290s	3280s	3280m	3280s	3260m	-NH ₂ stretch vibrations
3156s	3180s	3190s	3165m	3160m	3160s	3190s	3180s	
1617s	1600s	1607s	1610s	1600m	1612m	1607s	1614m	-NH ₂ deformation
1473s	1480m	1478s	1481w	1479s	1478s	1485s	1480s	-C-N asym. stretch
1413s	1442w	1450m	1422s	1438m	1435m	1445w	-	-C=S sym. stretch
	1390s	1395m	1390m	1400sh	1387m	1392s	1375m	
1086s	1090m	1080m	1105m	1102m	1095w	1095w	1120w	-NH ₂ rock
730s	720s	725m	718s	720s	718m	718s	715w	-C-N-sym. stretch
411m	409w	410w	415m	408m	412w	410w	410w	-NH ₂ torsional

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